

Communication Strategy and Toolkit - Final

DELIVERABLE 8.6

Marlen Töpfer, Lorena Caliman, Silke Davison
MAX WEBER STIFTUNG, UNIVERSITY OF COIMBRA, OAPEN | 22.08.2025

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Deliverable identifier	D8.6
Deliverable title	Communication Strategy and Toolkit - Final
Grant Agreement number	: 10107960
Project acronym	: OPERAS-PLUS
Project title	: On the road to sustainability: paving the way for OPERAS as an efficient open Social Sciences and Humanities scholarly communication Research Infrastructure
Funding Scheme	: HORIZON-INFRADEV-2021-DEV-02
Project's coordinator Organisation	: Max Weber Stiftung – MWS
E-mail address	: kaiser@maxweberstiftung.de
Website	: https://www.operas-eu.org/projects/operas-plus/
WP and tasks contributing	: WP8 Task 8.1
WP leader	: Max Weber Stiftung
Dissemination level	: Public (PU)
Due date	: 31.08.2025
Delivery date	: 22.08.2025
Authors	: Marlen Töpfer/MWS, Lorena Caliman/Universidade de Coimbra, Silke Davison/OAPEN

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Contributors : Elena Sokolova/OPERAS, Mateusz Franczak/IBL PAN, Drahomira Cupar/University of Zadar, Sy Holsinger/OPERAS, Yannick Legré/OPERAS, Aleš Pogačnik/ZRC SAZU, Elena Giglia/UniTo

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.16928317

This version has not yet been approved by the European Commission.

Document Log

Version	Date	Description	Name/Partner
ToC	2025-03-15	Table of Contents	Marlen Töpfer (MWS), Lorena Caliman (University of Coimbra)
v0.1	2025-05-30	First draft	Marlen Töpfer (MWS), Lorena Caliman (University of Coimbra)
v0.2	2025-07-21	Additional content regarding indicators and communication activities + future steps	Marlen Töpfer (MWS), Lorena Caliman (University of Coimbra), Silke Davison (OAPEN)
v0.2	2025-07-22	Internal Review	Mateusz Franczak (IBL PAN), Silke Davison (OAPEN)
v0.4	2025-07-23	Second draft, refinements	Marlen Töpfer (MWS), Lorena Caliman (University of Coimbra)
v0.5	2025-08-08	External Review	Carol Delmazo (OPERAS), Kelly Achenbach (MWS)
V0.6	2025-08-19	Final revision	Marlen Töpfer (MWS)
V1.0	2025-08-22	Final version for submission	Marlen Töpfer (MWS)

Abstract

This *Communication Strategy and Toolkit - Final* provides comprehensive documentation and evaluation of the communication activities carried out during the OPERAS-PLUS project. It emphasises the development, progress and expansion of the framework described in the Deliverable 8.1, the Communication Strategy and Toolkit, which was published in August 2023. This deliverable outlines the significant changes to the communication strategy and tools implemented throughout the project, reflecting on effective practices, encountered challenges, and the extent to which the defined indicators were achieved. The document concludes with a forward-looking perspective, offering reflections and recommendations on future communication strategies within the OPERAS Research Infrastructure as it moves towards becoming an ERIC by early 2028.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Contents

Contents	3
List of Abbreviations	4
Executive summary	8
1. Introduction	10
2. Further Development of the Communication Strategy	11
2.1. SWOT analysis	11
2.2. National Node Interviews	13
2.3. Identity & Positioning	14
2.4. Advanced Topic Expansion and Structure	17
3. Communication Toolbox and Assets	20
3.1. Visual Identity	20
3.1.1. Innovation Lab Logo	20
3.1.2. National Node Logos	20
3.1.3. New Social Media Templates	22
3.1.4. Business Cards and Signatures	26
4. Target Audiences and Stakeholders	27
4.1. OPERAS Personas	29
5. Communication and Dissemination Measures	33
5.1. Activities conducted	33
5.1.1. Internal Communication	33
5.1.2. Scientific publications and Zenodo	34
5.1.3. National Communities	35
5.1.4. Policy Briefs	36
5.1.5. Scientific Conferences, workshops & external events	37
5.1.6. Website	43
5.1.7. Blog (posts, series)	45
5.1.8. Newsletter	46
5.1.9. Social Media	46
5.1.9.1. New Social Media Strategy	47
5.1.9.2. Social Media Channels	50
5.1.10. Other Communication Materials	57
5.2. Indicators for communication	59
6. Post-OPERAS-PLUS: Reflections & Strategy	64
6.1. Coordination of all communication activities - toward a sustainable communication framework for OPERAS	64
6.2. National Nodes & local communication strategy	65
6.3. Recommendations for future projects	65

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
ABEU	Associação Brasileira das Editoras Universitárias
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AISBL	Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif (International Non-Profit Association)
AmeliCA	AmeliCA Open Science (collaborative initiative)
ATRIUM	Advancing fronTier Research In the arts and hUMANities
CC BY	Creative Commons
CLACSO	Consejo Latinoamericano de Ciencias Sociales
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
COESO	Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues
CONFOA	Conferência Luso-Brasileira de Acesso Aberto
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
DOAB	Directory of Open Access Books
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub

EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
erih+	European Reference Index for the Humanities and Social Sciences
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ESOF	EuroScience Open Forum
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FECYT	Fundación Española para la Ciencia y la Tecnología
FR	France
GER	Germany
GRAPHIA	Knowledge Graphs, AI Services and Next Generation Instrumentation for R&D in Social Sciences and Humanities
GraspOS	next Generation Research Assessment to Promote Open Science
IBL PAN	Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences
ID	Identifier
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LLMs	Large Language Models
LUMEN	Linked User-driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Network
MLE	Mutual Learning Exercise
OA	Open Access
OABN	Open Access Books Network

OAEBUDT	Open Access eBook Usage Data Trust
OAI	Open Archives Initiative
OAPEN	Open Access Publishing in European Networks
OASPA	Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association
OCT	OPERAS Coordination Team
OPERAS	open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities
OS	Open Science
PALOMERA	Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area
PL	Poland
PRISM	Peer Review Information Service for Monographs
PSNC	Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center
PUBMET	Conference on Scholarly Publishing in the Context of Open Science
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDA TIGER	Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions
RI	Research Infrastructure
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SIG	Special Interest Group
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities

SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
TSV	Federation of Finnish Learned Societies
UAEMéx	Universidad Autónoma del Estado de México
UC	University of Coimbra
UK	United Kingdom
UN	United Nations
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNGA78/79	78./79. General Assembly of the United Nations
VERA	Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation
WP7/WP8	Work Package 7 / 8
ZRC SAZU	Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts

Executive summary

This *Communication Strategy and Toolkit - Final* marks the culmination of the communication efforts developed and implemented throughout the OPERAS-PLUS project. Based on the foundation established in Deliverable 8.1¹, it reflects the development of the OPERAS communication strategy and toolkit in line with the maturing OPERAS Research Infrastructure (RI)² and its strategic transition to becoming a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) by 2028.

The strategy provides a structured and critical overview of the communication and dissemination activities that have taken place, outlining what was effective, what required adjustment, and how the communication approach was adapted to align with internal changes and the broader European Open Science landscape. In response to feedback from OPERAS members and National Nodes, particular efforts were made to clarify and strengthen the identity and positioning of OPERAS. In a dedicated 3-day workshop of the communication team in October 2024, the existing communication framework, as well as activities, have been evaluated and new strategies (see section 2.4 and in the following sections) were developed using the methodology of a SWOT-analysis and the feedback gathered from interviews with National Nodes' representatives. The strategy continues to address the needs of a diverse range of stakeholders, with the development of personas (see section 4.1) now enabling a more practical approach to meeting them.

Significant improvements have also been made to OPERAS' visual identity (see section 3.1), with the design being extended to reflect its development as a maturing infrastructure. New visual assets, including logos, templates, and presentation materials, were developed in collaboration with ZRC SAZU and are available via an accessible, expanded communication toolkit. This toolkit supports both internal and external stakeholders and will continue to evolve beyond the project's end.

A wide mix of communication tools and channels was used to support effective outreach and engagement, ranging from newsletters, blog posts, the website and policy briefs to the annual report, workshops, conferences, and social media outreach (primarily via LinkedIn and, earlier in the project, Twitter/X, and later also on Bluesky).

This final version also includes a review of communication-related indicators (see section 5.2) to help assess the reach and impact of activities conducted under Work Package 8 (WP8). Alongside the Monitoring Performance and Impact Dashboard and the Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (D 8.7), the strategy outlined in this document forms part of a comprehensive closing package for OPERAS-PLUS. It concludes with recommendations for future steps

¹ See Schulte, J., & Caliman, L. (2023). *Communication Strategy and Toolkit* (OPERAS-PLUS Deliverable 8.1) (v1.0 Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866207>.

² OPERAS is the Research Infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) in the European Research Area. Its mission is to coordinate and federate resources in Europe to efficiently address the scholarly communication needs of European researchers in the field of SSH.

to ensure that OPERAS' communication continues to support its visibility, stakeholder engagement, and strategic growth as it moves towards ERIC status.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

1. Introduction

The **OPERAS-PLUS Communication Strategy and Toolkit – Final** outlines the communication activities and developments implemented during the OPERAS-PLUS project period to support the project's goals and the broader objectives of OPERAS Research Infrastructure. It provides a comprehensive overview of all communication channels and activities carried out between September 2022 and August 2025.

This document does not reiterate the full communication strategy presented in Deliverable 8.1 but refers to it where relevant. It focuses on the concrete implementation of the strategy through specific actions across various channels and formats. Similarly, it does not repeat the toolkit section in detail but acknowledges the assets that were added and developed during the project.

This deliverable plays a key role in enhancing the future communication of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure and informing upcoming projects by identifying lessons learned, areas for improvement, and potential risks.

The structure and contents of this document are as follows:

- [Section 1](#): introduces the document and its structure.
- [Section 2](#): describes the further development of the communication strategy during the OPERAS-PLUS project period.
- [Section 3](#): outlines the expansion of the communication toolkit and assets, especially the visual identity.
- [Section 4](#): details the adjustment of the target audiences and their needs within the format of personas.
- [Section 5](#): covers all communication and dissemination measures and conducted activities, including a report on communication indicators.
- [Section 6](#): concludes the document with recommendations for a possible future communication strategy and tasks until the establishment of OPERAS as an ERIC.

2. Further Development of the Communication Strategy

The Communication Strategy serves as a guideline for all communication and dissemination activities of OPERAS Research Infrastructure (RI), and outlines how communication and dissemination efforts can support exploitation. During the project period, particularly following changes in the staff of the Work Package 8 (WP8) leadership in July 2024, the strategy was revised, analysed, and realigned to reflect current developments. These included the growing importance of Diamond Open Access (OA), the evolution and availability of services, additional core members in the Executive Assembly (FECYT from Spain, erih+ from Norway and TSV from Finland) and with that also different perspectives and topics, and broader political changes.

To support this assessment, the team held a focused three-day workshop in Bonn in October 2024, where they worked intensively on developing new approaches, assessing current communication trends, and conducting a brief benchmark analysis on other Research Infrastructures.

2.1. SWOT analysis

In October 2024, the Communication Team carried out a SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) during a workshop to assess their ongoing communications activities. SWOT analysis is a strategic planning method to identify and assess the internal and external factors that can impact a project, organisation, or activity. The aim of this exercise was to gain a clear and structured understanding of the current state of communications, identify internal strengths to build on, acknowledge weaknesses that require improvement, explore external opportunities for development, and highlight potential threats that could hinder progress. By pinpointing specific challenges, the team sought to develop targeted strategies and practical solutions to improve the overall effectiveness, coherence, and impact of their communications work. The outcomes of the analysis are presented in the table below.

Table 1 - OPERAS Communication SWOT analysis

<u>Strengths</u>	<u>Weaknesses</u>
<p>Identity & Positioning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Filling a gap as an infrastructure for Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) and open scholarly communication • Many topics are already identified <p>Communication Strategy/Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of the proposed strategy is already underway 	<p>Identity & Positioning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not enough visibility of the strengths • Definition of OPERAS (broad and not straightforward) • Service/project visibility as from OPERAS (branding) <p>Communication Strategy/Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discrepancy between communications strategy and actions

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key messages are designed for related target audiences <p>Internal</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help of many institutions for communications (needs to be structured) • A variety of content is available from all the diverse work of OPERAS as a Research Infrastructure (RI) • Good services vision • Extra marketing service team 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are we reaching our target audience? • Little storytelling so no real strategy for the key messages • Actions are not defined for each channel • A lot of social media channels • SEO could be improved <p>Internal</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some processes not set up • Services still in development • Minimal budget • Few employees • Knowledge of topics are not directly related to knowledge of OPERAS • Fragmentation of roles in channels/lack of alignment • Communication flow within OPERAS
<p style="text-align: center;"><u>Opportunities</u></p> <p>Topics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diamond OA movement • Trust/Disinformation • Research assessment • Open Science <p>Status</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Already on the ESFRI roadmap • LinkedIn presence is growing • National communities involved and developing • International communities/collaboration <p>Audiences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diverse audiences • Lots of interest from current audiences 	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>Threats</u></p> <p>Current Developments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governmental changes in Europe • Not becoming an ERIC • X (formerly Twitter) • Information overload overall (and also inside of OPERAS) <p>Audience/Identity & Positioning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diverse audience • People go elsewhere to find information • Closeness with OPENAIRE, DARIAH, CLARIN <p>Internal</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not getting enough money • Information overload overall (and also inside of OPERAS)

The **key results** can be summarised as:

- OPERAS has a clear mission and strong foundation, but its strengths lack visibility and its identity remains too broad.
- There is a richness of content and institutional support, but communication efforts are fragmented and lack coordination.
- The existing communication strategy is not fully implemented, with unclear messaging, channels' use, and audience targeting.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

- OPERAS can benefit from current trends like Diamond OA and Open Science, as well as its growing presence and networks.
- Limited resources, internal fragmentation, and external competition pose risks to effective communication and audience engagement.

In the following chapters, strategies and actions are outlined to address these challenges and leverage the potential of OPERAS as a Research Infrastructure. Addressing the results is an ongoing process, as is reflected in the following sections.

2.2. National Node Interviews

In 2021, OPERAS began establishing “National Nodes”, the core members of OPERAS as institutions across Europe that are well respected and connected within their national communities. Through this set-up, National Nodes agree to connect OPERAS to local stakeholders to identify their needs and provide relevant services and training. Conversely, National Nodes and their local networks have a wealth of knowledge to share with the larger scholarly community. For example, they are well placed to find balanced solutions for maintaining national languages as valid modes of scientific expression while promoting them internationally. Through their cooperation with OPERAS, National Nodes help aggregate existing approaches and resources from within national communities and bring them to the European level.³

To further support its case for becoming an ERIC, OPERAS sought to gain a better understanding of national perspectives and landscapes. In September/October 2024, OPERAS conducted interviews with representatives of all thirteen National Nodes: Croatia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Poland, Portugal, the Netherlands, Norway, Slovenia, Spain and the United Kingdom. Each node representative was asked questions about OPERAS' role in supporting the community, OPERAS as a recognised infrastructure, its services and outputs, and the specifications within each national Open Science and research landscape. The interviews were transcribed, analysed with key responses, and structured into a database. Miro⁴ was used to compile case studies and success stories, which were organised into different sections. As the interviews were confidential, only some examples in the form of screenshots of the Miro board can be viewed below. In this case, the focus is on OPERAS' services, community and network building, as well as reflecting on the potential of OPERAS as a Research Infrastructure.

³ See also more on the engagement of National Nodes and their role, Caliman Fontes, L., Franczak, M., Avanço, K., Töpfer, M., Giglia, E., & Leão, D. (2025). Roadmap for the implementation of National Nodes - final - Deliverable 7.3 OPERAS-PLUS. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15533121>.

⁴ Miro is a visual workspace for innovation that enables distributed teams to work together and visualise ideas and work on projects collaboratively, see www.miro.com.

Figure 1: Collection of case studies/success stories of the OPERAS services

Figure 2: Collection of case studies/success stories on community & network building

2.3. Identity & Positioning

Throughout the project, OPERAS has continued to strengthen its identity as the leading European Research Infrastructure dedicated to open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH). Its unique positioning lies in addressing a critical gap by supporting research community-led, non-profit, and multilingual publishing practices that align with the principles of Open Science. As the landscape around Diamond Open Access, research

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

assessment reform, and equitable knowledge dissemination evolves, OPERAS has maintained a clear commitment to fostering collaboration across national and disciplinary boundaries. The infrastructure's presence on the ESFRI roadmap further reinforces its strategic relevance, while its growing engagement with National Nodes, international partners, and diverse stakeholder communities reflects its role as a connector and facilitator in the broader SSH ecosystem. Continued efforts to refine OPERAS' visual identity, messaging, and visibility have contributed to greater recognition and understanding of its mission across audiences.

That said, it also became clear that one of OPERAS' main target audiences — researchers — often struggle to grasp what OPERAS actually represents. This was echoed in feedback gathered during the National Nodes interviews, where several respondents noted that OPERAS is difficult to describe due to its broad scope, diverse activities, and the range of topics it addresses. As a result, Work Package 8 and the Communication Taskforce⁵ undertook a reflection process on how OPERAS is defined, including the identification of relevant keywords and terms that best describe its identity. The following provides an insight into the work carried out:

Figure 3: Ideas for a better definition of OPERAS

⁵ The Communication Taskforce is a bimonthly meeting where the core communication team meets communication officers from projects, the OPERAS capacity building manager, OPERAS services team and the OPERAS National Nodes liaison. Depending on the needs of the team, more people could be invited to specific task force meetings. These meetings are used to further align communication in the broader circle of OPERAS community and projects, and to boost efforts and results jointly with the input of a diverse set of professionals.

Figure 4: Keywords related to OPERAS and ranked

Figure 5: Collection of keywords related to OPERAS

Following these reflections, revised definitions of OPERAS were drafted, which are currently under review by the appropriate OPERAS bodies.

2.4. Advanced Topic Expansion and Structure

As stated in the previous communication strategy submitted at the end of July 2023 (D8.1) the communication strategy is aligned with the pillars and objectives of the OPERAS strategic plan 2023-2025 (see Figure 6 below).

Figure 6: OPERAS strategic plan 2023–2025

During the project period, it became clear that communication not only supports the strategic objectives and pillars, but that it also benefits from a more dynamic and topic-driven approach.

Originally, as outlined in the initial communication strategy at the beginning of the project, the following elements were identified as the central topic areas for communication:

- Research Infrastructure,
- Services,
- Special Interest Groups,
- National Communities,
- OPERAS Innovation Lab,
- FAIR support in the EOSC ecosystem,
- Projects.

These were defined more as structural groups and activities that required communication coverage, and served as a starting point for campaign development. However, as the project progressed, it became evident that these areas could be made more effective by reorganising them into thematic topics, better aligned with actual engagement needs and community interests.

To this end, in the communication workshop in October 2024 the communication team reflected on the effectiveness of the current communication topics and structures. This evaluation was complemented by insights gained from interviews with National Nodes, which provided practical feedback on what resonates best in national and local contexts.

As a result of this combined evaluation, a refined list of topics was developed. These reflect both strategic priorities and community-driven interest areas, and offer a more actionable structure for communication planning:

- **OPERAS & Community & SIGs & National Nodes** – this major topic includes activities that are present in the daily life of the infrastructure.
 - **Open Access Books**

OPERAS is highly involved in initiatives related to Open Access Books, such as the PALOMERA project⁶ and the OAEBUDT programme⁷ (as a fiscal host). There is also a Special Interest Group within OPERAS dedicated to the topic.

- **Multilingualism**

OPERAS' role in Multilingualism dates from many years now, with the creation of the Multilingualism Special Interest Group in 2018. Also involved and co-leading the Translations and Open Science project, OPERAS is continuously involved in the advocacy for supporting national languages as scientific ones.

- **Research Assessment**

One of the current pressing topics in Open Science, research assessment reform is being also integrated in the OPERAS community via its members' engagement in external projects and initiatives, but also leading the SSH Pilot within the GraspOS project⁸, which is directly related to the topic.

- **Services** – raising awareness of the services included in the OPERAS service catalogue (GoTriple, Pathfinder, Metrics, VERA, Hypotheses, PRISM) is a continuous effort of the OPERAS communication team, making this overall topic one very present in the daily communication updates; with the following subtopics:

- **Citizen Science**

OPERAS is engaged in Citizen Science with the development of the VERA platform⁹, dedicated to citizen science and participatory research in social sciences and humanities and the previous project COESO¹⁰.

- **Innovation Lab**

The OPERAS Innovation Lab¹¹ is a continued effort of OPERAS dedicated to researching user needs and developing prototypes of innovative services and tools tailored for the academic environment. The Innovation Lab subcampaign highlights and features the Lab's continuous development and projects.

- **Projects** – a specific overall campaign for OPERAS projects aims to give the community the opportunity to engage with the projects' consortia, events and topics, and to showcase OPERAS involvement in them, featuring a variety of topics.

⁶ See <https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/>.

⁷ Open Access Books Usage Data Trust Effort, see <https://operas-eu.org/projects/oa-book-usage-data-trust/>.

⁸ See <https://graspos.eu/>.

⁹ See <https://vera.operas-eu.org/>.

¹⁰ See <https://coeso.hypotheses.org/>.

¹¹ See <https://lab.operas-eu.org/>.

- **Diamond Open Access (EDCH)** – as part of OPERAS already established path advocating for Diamond Open Access, the launch of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH)¹², fiscally hosted by OPERAS, reinforces the infrastructure’s commitment to this. The campaign also aims to engage and inform the community about its developments.

This refined topic structure enables a more flexible and audience-specific communication approach. It allows campaigns and content to be better tailored to stakeholder groups, while maintaining alignment with the broader strategic framework. This structure was also used to establish the new social media strategy (see section 5.1.9), ensuring consistency across communication channels and enhancing topic visibility.

¹² See <https://diamas.org/>.

3. Communication Toolbox and Assets

During the final period of the project, the communications toolkit was further expanded and refined. Hosted on an accessible shared drive, it now includes a comprehensive set of OPERAS and OPERAS-PLUS materials, with several additional templates, visual assets, and updated logos developed in response to emerging needs. These resources remain openly available to all OPERAS members and will partly continue to be accessible via the OPERAS website. Throughout the project, OPERAS has actively encouraged its members to represent the infrastructure at relevant events and meetings. The continuous updates to the toolkit ensured it remained a practical and evolving resource, aligned with the consortium’s communication objectives and the growing visibility of OPERAS.

3.1. Visual Identity

The visual identity of the infrastructure was further developed during the project period, starting in August 2023, to reflect its evolving role as a Research Infrastructure on the path to becoming an ERIC. This updated identity was created in close collaboration with a designer from ZRC SAZU, one of OPERAS’ core members, and includes the following assets.

3.1.1. Innovation Lab Logo

Figure 7 – OPERAS Innovation Lab logo

Figure 8 - version of the OPERAS Innovation Lab logo to be used in special occasions when there is a combination of OPERAS logos and the Lab’s logo together

The creation of the Innovation Lab logo was concluded in April 2025.

3.1.2. National Node Logos

The creation of the National Node logos was a natural consequence of the development of the national communities along OPERAS-PLUS. Initially, the

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS’s view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

national communities were represented only by their names and the logos of their national leads. With the project, along with the regular meetings among the nodes representatives and the OPERAS communication team, the logos were first created and then updated with their current colours, which now represent either one of OPERAS visual identity colours or a colour representing the country (via their flags or national culture) - whereas before, the colours were selected only from OPERAS' corporate palette, sometimes resulting in duplicates.

The process of adapting the preferred colours of each Node was documented via the Communication Team shared drive and is reproduced below:

B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
National Node	Colour	Colour Details	Tagline	Translation							
OPERAS-ES	Spanish flag Gold #F1E21F	CMYK 0/6/87/5 RGB 241/226/31 HEX #F1E21F	open scholarly communication in the european research area for the social sciences and humanities / Spanish National Node								
OPERAS-FI	BLUE from the Finnish flag	HEX #002F6C CMYK 100-58-0-58 RGB 0-47-108	open scholarly communication in the european research area for the social sciences and humanities / Finnish National Node		OPERAS colours	Light Yellow	CMYK 0/23/55/0 RGB 253/200/130 HEX #FEC982				
OPERAS-FR	OPERAS peach	CMYK 0/76/54/0 RGB 241/100/101 HEX #F16465	open scholarly communication in the european research area for the social sciences and humanities / French National Node	Communication scientifique ouverte dans l'espace européen de la recherche pour les sciences humaines et sociales / Nœud national français		Dark Yellow	CMYK 0/38/92/0 RGB 250/168/45 HEX #FBA92E				
OPERAS-GER	Logo green from before	RGB: 147/193/28 CMYK 50/0 / 100/0 # 93c11c	open scholarly communication in the european research area for the social sciences and humanities / German National Node	not needed, cannot be translated properly		Light Turquoise	CMYK 66/0/32/0 RGB 65/190/186 HEX #42C0BB				
OPERAS-GR	red from institution	Red Pepper Hex #B8112A RGB 187, 17, 42 CMYK 0, 87, 57, 27	open scholarly communication in the european research area for the social sciences and humanities / Greek National Node	ανοικτή επιστημονική επικοινωνία στον ευρωπαϊκό χώρο έρευνας για τις κοινωνικές και ανθρωπιστικές επιστήμες / Ελληνικός Εθνικός Κύβος		Dark Turquoise	CMYK 92/57/44/23 RGB 15/86/104 HEX #115669				
OPERAS-HR	blue from institution	RGB 28 73 116 CMYK 94/70/37/22, #1c496a	open scholarly communication in the european research area for the social sciences and humanities / Croatian National Node	otvorena znanstvena komunikacija u Europskom istraživačkom prostoru za društvene i humanističke znanosti / hrvatski ogranak		Peach	CMYK 0/76/54/0 RGB 241/100/101 HEX #F16465				
OPERAS-IT	Red from national flag (Pantone 19-1662)	CMYK 0/84/80/20 RGB 205/33/42 HEX #CD212A	open scholarly communication in the european research area for the social sciences and humanities / Italian National Node	comunicazione scientifica aperta per le scienze umane e sociali nello spazio europeo della ricerca/ Nodo nazionale italiano		Light violet	CMYK 17/44/0/0 RGB 205/155/199 HEX #CD98C7				
OPERAS-NL	OPERAS dark yellow	CMYK 0/38/92/0 RGB 250/168/45 HEX #FBA92E	open scholarly communication in the european research area for the social sciences and humanities / Dutch National Node	Ronald Srijder would you mind putting a Dutch translation here if it's possible/makes sense to translate?		Light blue	CMYK 58/14/14/0 RGB 103/177/204 HEX #67B1CC				
OPERAS-NO	OPERAS light blue	CMYK 58/14/14/0 RGB 103/177/204 HEX #67B1CC	open scholarly communication in the european research area for the social sciences and humanities / Norwegian National Node								
OPERAS-PL	blue from institution	CMYK 100/30/0/11 RGB 0, 159, 227 HEX #0099e3	open scholarly communication in the european research area for the social sciences and humanities / Polish National Node	Otwarta komunikacja w humanistyce i naukach społecznych w Polsce							
OPERAS-PT	change to flag green - #006600	CMYK 100-35-100-30 RGB 0-102-0 HEX #006600	open scholarly communication in the european research area for the social sciences and humanities / Portuguese National Node								
OPERAS-SI	OPERAS light turquoise	CMYK 66/0/32/0 RGB 65/190/186 HEX #42C0BB	open scholarly communication in the european research area for the social sciences and humanities / Slovenian National Node	odprta znanstvena komunikacija v evropskem raziskovalnem prostoru za družboslovje in humanistiko /slovensko nacionalno vozlišče							
OPERAS-UK	OPERAS dark turquoise	CMYK 92/57/44/23 RGB 15/86/104 HEX #115669	open scholarly communication in the european research area for the social sciences and humanities / UK National Node								

Figure 9 - Table of the National Node logo colours definition

The final National Node logos as of the end of the OPERAS-PLUS project are as follows.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Figure 10 - Collection of current National Node logos

3.1.3. New Social Media Templates

Following the reorganisation and tailoring of the OPERAS visual identity inside OPERAS-PLUS, the communication team has created new templates for use on the infrastructure's social media channels. The aim was to provide a visual alignment of OPERAS topics and regular posting, generating a steady identification of the topics in place. The templates were created and shared on OPERAS Canva account¹³, facilitating their use and adaptation.

¹³ Canva is an easy to use design tool that enables collaboration and visual creation, www.canva.com.

After the reorganisation of the OPERAS YouTube channel¹⁴, the team also put together a series of aligned thumbnails to improve the usage and navigation on the OPERAS channel.

For the OPERAS blog¹⁵, the social media templates were adapted to align with the specific dimensions used on the Hypotheses platform.

OPERAS Community, SIGs & National Nodes

Figure 11 - Community templates, allowing adaptations for National Nodes, SIGs, and topics

Services

Figure 12 – Template for OPERAS Services (VERA example)

¹⁴ See <https://www.youtube.com/@operas-eu>.

¹⁵ See <https://operas.hypotheses.org/>.

Projects

Figures 13 – Examples of project template versions tailored to each project's colours

Diamond/EDCH

Figure 14 – EDCH templates versions

News

Figure 15 – News template versions with examples

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Events

Figure 16 – Event template versions with examples

YouTube Thumbnails

The OPERAS YouTube thumbnails follow a simple yet aligned identity, using gradient colours background and the logos of initiatives involved, besides the OPERAS logo and the appropriate EU funding information. Below are some examples of thumbnails created to organise the YouTube channel home.

OPERAS services

OPERAS service - VERA

Public · Playlist
View full playlist

OPERAS service - GoTriple

Public · Playlist
View full playlist

OPERAS service - PRISM

Public · Playlist
View full playlist

Projects OPERAS is/was involved in

[View all](#)

GRAPHIA

Public · Playlist
View full playlist

ALMASI

Public · Playlist
View full playlist

FASCA

Public · Playlist
View full playlist

DIAMAS

Public · Playlist
View full playlist

CRAFT-OA

Public · Playlist
View full playlist

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Figure 17 - OPERAS YouTube thumbnails collection

3.1.4. Business Cards and Signatures

Another set of corporate visual identity products are the OPERAS AISBL team’s business cards and signatures, which have a subtle but steady importance in reinforcing the OPERAS unity across channels, including email exchange and corporate networking.

Figure 18 – Business card example, front and back

Figure 19 - E-mail signature example

4. Target Audiences and Stakeholders

OPERAS' target audiences have been refined over time through a series of adjustments and reviews. In the first version of this communication strategy, the target audiences were distributed in the categories of "internal", "internal and external", and "external", besides the specific category of users of the services. As pointed out in the previous version, we have used a Power and Interest approach¹⁶ to better understand which stakeholder groups we wanted to engage with, and to work in order to move from information and satisfaction to collaboration and engagement¹⁷.

The subsequent review of the stakeholder groups, towards the end of the OPERAS-PLUS project, envisioned a way of better engaging and targeting these groups. The team recognised that a long list of stakeholders was not the best option to be efficient in addressing their needs. With that in mind, the OPERAS Communication Taskforce and the OPERAS-PLUS Work Package 8 have both contributed to the revision of the groups, resulting in a slightly shorter list. The revision work was also recorded in a Miro Board (see figure 20), through which the different OPERAS communication working groups, such as the Communication Taskforce and WP8, have contributed by choosing the stakeholders they deem best fit the Research Infrastructure missions.

During the review, it became clear that a simpler division would best facilitate engagement and exchange with the audiences. So, instead of having the four categories of before (internal, internal & external, external and services users), the new version brings simply two categories: internal and external audiences. The final and current result of the stakeholder groups and target audiences review can be seen in table 2 below.

Figure 20 – Process of reviewing and refining OPERAS stakeholder groups (Miro Board)

¹⁶ Vincenz-Donnelly, Lisa, Pieruschka, Roland, & Haley, Natalie. (2020). RI-VIS D4.2 Communication Strategy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4090929>, p. 4.

¹⁷ See Communication Strategy and Toolkit (OPERAS-PLUS Deliverable 8.1). Available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/7866207>.

Table 2 – List of audiences and OPERAS stakeholder groups
after review during the OPERAS-PLUS project

Internal
OPERAS members (Core Members, Ordinary Members, Supporting Members)
OPERAS Scientific Advisory Committee
Special Interest Groups
OPERAS General Assembly
OPERAS Board of Governing Bodies
Projects Communication Officers and Project Coordinators
National Nodes
External
Research performing organisations & SSH Researchers
Public and university libraries
Small and academic publishers
Policy makers and funders
Citizens and civil society organisations
Potential users of services
Service providers
Learned societies

As seen from the table and the comparing Miro Board overview, the list of stakeholders was radically shortened, allowing related groups to be held together – for example, Research Performing Organisations and researchers. These two “groups” of stakeholders can be actually reached like one, given that RPOs are fundamentally composed of researchers. Therefore, communication efforts targeting RPOs will also reach researchers in the same manner and with the same effort. Similarly, for groups such as policy makers and funders within the context of Research Infrastructures, the approach applies to them as decision makers.

As target audiences of OPERAS activities, the different stakeholder groups are defined to guide the communication team to tailor messaging for each particular target group, emphasising the value of OPERAS in respect to their needs. More on messaging can be found in the OPERAS-PLUS D8.1¹⁸.

4.1. OPERAS Personas

As mentioned in the previous subsection, in the initial phases of the OPERAS communication strategy, the team focused on highly specific and narrowly defined target groups. While this approach allowed for deep audience insights, it also limited the broader reach and flexibility of the communication efforts. To ensure OPERAS' messaging remains inclusive, scalable, and adaptable across various contact points, we decided to expand the scope of our target audiences. This approach allows us to streamline our list of target groups. This shift enables us to address a wider range of stakeholders while still maintaining relevance and clarity in our communication.

In order not to lose the specificity of each target group, we developed five representative personas¹⁹ that capture the diversity within our now-expanded audience. These personas help us understand key motivations, behaviours, and expectations, and serve as a practical foundation for crafting effective and resonant communication strategies. Personas are essential in communication strategies because they translate abstract audience segments into relatable, human-centered profiles, helping us design targeted and meaningful messages that truly resonate. The following section presents these five personas in detail.

¹⁸ Pages 23 to 27: <https://zenodo.org/records/7866207>.

¹⁹ "Personas are fictional profiles that represent groups of similar people in a target audience. They can help you figure out how to reach people on a more personal level, while delivering the right messages, offers, and products at the right time" (Think with Google). Available at: <https://www.thinkwithgoogle.com/future-of-marketing/creativity/marketing-personas-audience-research/>.

SSH researcher

MARY SHELLEY

"Hi, I'm Mary and doing my PhD in Berlin in literature with a focus on gender studies. I'm very interested in the presentation of feminine behaviour in literature. Because I stand for openness and equality, I want to publish OA."

- 29 years old
- Researcher
- PhD, Literature
- from UK, based Berlin

LIFE/WORK SITUATION

- Likely on a short term contract, therefore under pressure to publish a lot to be considered for a contract renewal
- Closely involved with RPOs, to some extent contact with RFOs, libraries, publishers

Recognised in work environment

- Talks a lot about her PhD and asks a lot of questions
- Is really motivated and has a lot of innovative ideas

USE OF TECHNOLOGY & TECHNICAL EXPERTISE

- Uses collaborative tools such as GoogleDocs and research tools, e.g. for analysis, creation + curation of datasets and literature review
- Quickly adapts to using new ones

GOALS

- To become a professor and make a difference in her research area
- Have an impact on society
- Fight inequality and discrimination

GAINS

- Professional development: Reach a broad audience, be recognised by peers
- international experience
- Part of innovative approaches

JOBS TO BE DONE

- To do research on her topic and publish articles
- Find people to collaborate with
- Present research at conferences

PAINS

- Lost, overwhelmed, feels isolated with her research
- doesn't find a lot of info about publishing her research

COMMUNICATION CHANNELS & BEHAVIOUR

- Social Media

- > checks for job updates regularly, posts about research.
- Newsletters, email

Librarian

IVANA HORVAT

"Hi, I'm Ivana Horvat and I've been working in a library for 25 years as an expert in e-resources. I support Open Access through acquisition, technical support, and training. My role is to help researchers navigate data and ensure knowledge and their research is openly accessible."

- 52 years old
- Librarian, expert in e-resources
- Master's degree Library & Information science
- Croatian, based in Zadar

LIFE/WORK SITUATION

- Has worked in a library for 25 years, is responsible for implementing and maintaining the OA repository
- Involved in OS infrastructures, European projects and active in a national librarian society

Recognised in work environment

- Well connected
- Always complains about lack of funding & criticises a lot in general
- stresses importance of librarians as mediators with publishers

USE OF TECHNOLOGY & TECHNICAL EXPERTISE

- Skilled in metadata management and technical standards
- Repository systems, OA platforms
- Comfortable with structured workflows
- Prefers using a desktop

GOALS

- Develop and improve the library repository
- Promote and support OS and RDM principles
- Support researchers with training on OA

GAINS

- Improved library catalog
- Stronger institutional reputation in Open Science
- Opportunities for collaboration in European infrastructures

JOBS TO BE DONE

- Documentation, referencing, and indexing
- Training researchers
- Technical support for OA
- Manage & apply data/metadata standards

PAINS

- Chronic lack of funding & HR
- Overworked
- Need to constantly justify OA investments
- not confident in English
- difficult to find latest developments on OA & implement

COMMUNICATION CHANNELS & BEHAVIOUR

- Social Media

- Newsletters, mailing lists, website
- Phone calls, meetings
- follows recommendations from other librarians

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Publisher/Editor

PABLO GARCIA

"Hi, I am Pablo and I work for an university press in Spain. For the past 7 years, I've been leading the OA department, focusing on how to implement Open Access models. I am interested in ongoing developments in OA and contribute with my editorial perspective to the debate."

- 42 years old
- Editor, Head of OA Department
- Degree in Editorial Studies, Master's in Philosophy
- Spain

LIFE/WORK SITUATION

- Worked in editorial after completing a BA and went back to study for a MPhil focusing on scholarly publishing
- Started working as an intern in his institution before becoming an Editor

Recognised in work environment

- Talkative, always contributes with evidence-based insights
- Aware of stakeholder status
- Clear and structured

USE OF TECHNOLOGY & TECHNICAL EXPERTISE

- Uses smartphone and tablet often
- Starting to work with AI
- Open to new technologies and has a big team of developers to draw on

GOALS

- Wants to ensure that OA can fund the work of the press and changing to OA will benefit their image as a publisher but also their work
- Wants to be up-to-date with every development

GAINS

- To be recognised in the publishing house and as a person
- To keep up with the trends and developments

JOB TO BE DONE

- Transition to OA, research business models
- Manage new systems and keep money in mind
- Attend lots of meetings

PAINS

- Receives lots of emails
- Often criticised about his role as a publishing house
- Has to deal with budget adjustments

COMMUNICATION CHANNELS & BEHAVIOUR

- Social Media → engages in comments and discussions
- Newsletters, email

SSH open scholarly advocate

MARION LEROY

"Hi, I'm Marion and I've been working for 10 years in European organisations to promote Open Science in SSH. I connect communities and infrastructures to strengthen SSH. My goal is to make SSH research more visible and accessible internationally"

- 39 years old
- OA advocate
- M.A. Art history
- France, everywhere in Europe

LIFE/WORK SITUATION

- Works in European infrastructures and projects, often also as advisor
- Constantly on the move, attends many conferences
- Bridges researchers, infrastructures, and policymakers

Recognised in work environment

- Frequently advocates for SSH interests in policy discussions.
- Energetic, talkative, and highly visible in Open Science networks

USE OF TECHNOLOGY & TECHNICAL EXPERTISE

- Heavy smartphone user (always on the move)
- Uses online collaboration tools
- always looking for new tools

GOALS

- Raise international visibility of SSH.
- Advocate for OA policies.
- Ensure SSH is represented in infrastructures

GAINS

- Stronger role of SSH in Open Science
- Wider recognition and networks

JOB TO BE DONE

- Represent SSH in European discussions
- Connect communities and projects
- Spread knowledge at events

PAINS

- Talks a lot, often critical
- Gets too many emails
- Feels SSH is undervalued vs. STEM

COMMUNICATION CHANNELS & BEHAVIOUR

- Social Media → posts a lot of statements & shares
- Reads newsletters, prefers short emails

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Figures 21 to 25 - OPERAS Personas

5. Communication and Dissemination Measures

The OPERAS-PLUS WP8 has identified a set of key dissemination measures to support the project's outreach efforts. Below is an overview of the main activities carried out during the project period. Starting from the end of 2024, these activities have been increasingly aligned with the new topics defined in section 2.4. of this document.

5.1. Activities conducted

At the beginning of the OPERAS-PLUS project, a table within the communication strategy²⁰ outlined the planned dissemination measures to promote the infrastructure and its activities over the period of the project. In the following section, all communication activities carried out during the project period are listed, described, and evaluated. This includes an assessment of potential risks encountered, as well as reflections on what was well received and what proved less effective. The activities are structured according to their type and the communication channels used.

5.1.1. Internal Communication

The communication channels of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure are divided into internal and external. The internal communication channels include different **mailing lists**, for reaching the different groups inside the infrastructure, such as the General Assembly, the Executive Assembly, the Scientific Advisory Board, and the infrastructure's member community. There are also specific mailing lists for the projects.²¹

In addition to mailing lists, OPERAS members make extensive use of **Mattermost** as an instant open-source messaging service. Mattermost is used to join topic-specific groups, exchange daily information, and share quick updates across the infrastructure. From 2023 to mid-2025, usage significantly increased: starting with 7 workspaces, 116 channels, 205 users, and 14,593 messages exchanged in 2023, it grew to 12 workspaces, 370 channels, 560 users, and 317,273 messages exchanged by the end of June 2025.

OPERAS also uses **Confluence** as an internal knowledge hub for information management and documentation. During the project period, a dedicated communication section was created to support the OPERAS Coordination Team and the Executive Assembly by providing structured access to key documents, communication workflows, and decisions. This has helped strengthen internal transparency and streamline communication processes.

²⁰ See page 34 in Schulte, J., & Caliman, L. (2023). Communication Strategy and Toolkit (OPERAS-PLUS Deliverable 8.1) (v1.0 Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866207>.

²¹ Find more about the internal organisation and communication structure in the D3.1 & D3.4 – Report on the activities of OPERAS' bodies of WP3, see Manista, F., Avanço, K., Dumouchel, S., LEGRÉ, Y., & Mounier, P. (2025). Report on the activities of OPERAS bodies - Final (OPERAS-PLUS Deliverable 3.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15411164>.

The internal **Communication Taskforce**, composed of members from the OPERAS Coordination Team (OCT) working on communication, as well as communication staff from various projects in which OPERAS is involved, was restructured in October 2024 to meet more regularly and strategically. From that point on, the group began convening every other week to discuss ongoing developments and communication activities, and in the following meeting to work together on specific topics, such as the social media strategy, website updates, OPERAS identity and AI and communication.

Given the dynamic growth of OPERAS and its expanding presence across European and international research landscapes, it became evident that stronger coordination and more structured communication management is required (see also the SWOT analysis in section 2.1). This more structural coordination approach aims to ensure consistent messaging across all channels and activities, avoid duplication of efforts, and provide all involved parties with a clearer overview of ongoing initiatives and shared priorities. Further reflection on this can be found in the final section, under point 6.1.

5.1.2. Scientific publications and Zenodo

OPERAS also contributed with (**scientific**) **articles** on the project, its objectives, workflows and results to journals or chapters in books, such as:

- Delmazo, C. & Smaniotto, A. (2025). How the VERA Platform Helps Citizen Scientists Collaborate. *Katina*: <https://doi.org/10.1146/katina-20250205-1>.
- Avanço, K. & Gingold, A., (2022) “FAIRifying a scholarly publishing service: Methodology based on the OpenEdition’s internal FAIR audit”, *The Journal of Electronic Publishing* 25(2). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3998/jep.1540>.
- Associação Brasileira das Editoras Universitárias - ABEU. (2022). Editoras universitárias: desafios contemporâneos [Livro acadêmico; PDF]. In R. V. Argollo & F. G. Rosa (Eds.), *Associação Brasileira das Editoras Universitárias - ABEU* (p.165). https://abeu.org.br/documents/30/EDITORAS_UNIVERSITARIAS_desafios_contemporaneos.pdf.
- Roos, M., & Bang, M. (2024). Reshaping and a makeover – preparing old services for new times. *Septentrio Conference Series*, (1). <https://doi.org/10.7557/5.7796>.
- Perdomo, T. M., García, M. I. C., Leão, D., & Castillo, L. (2024). *Tendencia Editorial UR número 37 - Especial*. https://doi.org/10.12804/issn.2382-3135_10336.43897_teur.

Zenodo²² is used as an open-access repository to deposit and disseminate OPERAS-PLUS project outputs—such as deliverables, research papers, posters, and presentations—under open licenses (preferably CC BY), each assigned a DOI for persistent access. All publications are grouped under the Zenodo community “OPERAS: open scholarly communication in the European research area for social sciences and humanities” (identifier: *operaseu*), which includes outputs

²² See <https://zenodo.org/>. OPERAS community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/operaseu/>.

from OPERAS-PLUS, related projects, and National Nodes. Metadata guidelines ensure consistent documentation across all uploads. During the whole project period **242 publications** have been uploaded or added to the OPERAS Zenodo community (as of end of June 2025).

5.1.3. National Communities

During the OPERAS-PLUS project, three **new core members joined OPERAS** and committed to establishing National Nodes in their respective countries. These core members are TSV (Finland), FECYT (Spain), and erih+ (Norway).

While some of the OPERAS National Nodes, such as OPERAS-GER (Germany) and OPERAS-PL (Poland), had already been active and running activities prior to the OPERAS-PLUS project, others began establishing their national node during the course of OPERAS-PLUS. To support this development, a **National Node Roadmap**²³ was created within WP7 of the OPERAS-PLUS project to guide National Nodes in their set-up.

Since November 2021, National Node representatives have been meeting monthly to discuss pressing topics, including communication. For this reason, the communication team has consistently participated—both to share updates on ongoing communication activities and to gather the specific communication needs of the National Nodes. The meeting was officially renamed to the **National Node Committee** in March 2025.

In parallel, the National Nodes expressed a shared interest in a dedicated **communication workshop**, which was held on the 4th and 11th of April 2025 (1.5 hours each). The workshop provided a reflective and collaborative space to assess OPERAS' current communication landscape. Participants shared perceptions of OPERAS, exchanged insights into national communication practices, and addressed challenges related to tools, workflows, and messaging. The sessions also included a review of internal resources, a brief discussion on corporate language, and concluded with an open exchange to identify areas for future improvement.

Specific communication activities across the National Nodes are outlined in the final National Node Roadmap²⁴, published in May 2025, and an overview of their current status and initiatives can be found in the OPERAS Annual Report 2024²⁵.

²³ See Caliman, L., & Leão, D. (2023). Roadmap for the Implementation of OPERAS National Nodes (OPERAS-PLUS Deliverable 7.2) (v1.0 Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8289238>.

²⁴ See Caliman Fontes, L., Franczak, M., Avanço, K., Töpfer, M., Giglia, E., & Leão, D. (2025). Roadmap for the implementation of National Nodes - final - Deliverable 7.3 OPERAS-PLUS. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15533121>.

²⁵ See OPERAS, Töpfer, M., Caliman Fontes, L., & Semolič, N. (2025). Annual Report 2024. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15672537>, page 41-50.

5.1.4. Policy Briefs

As part of our communication efforts, we have developed a series of policy briefs on specific topics, which effectively convey key issues, findings and recommendations to policymakers and relevant stakeholders. A policy brief is a concise document that either advocates a particular position or objectively outlines a policy issue alongside available options and recommendations. As the OPERAS-PLUS project is funded under the Horizon Europe Infra-Dev framework (grant agreement ID: 101079608), OPERAS used the European Commission template.

Additionally, recognising that some topics are particularly relevant to national or local contexts within our community, we created additional Community Policy Briefs for some topics. These were developed in a more flexible format to better address specific needs, allowing for a more in-depth explanation and contextualisation of key issues. This multifaceted approach ensures that both EU-level and local stakeholders are effectively informed and engaged.

Below is a list of the policy briefs written and published during the OPERAS-PLUS project:

- **EC Policy Briefs - Research Infrastructures - Aug 2025²⁶:**
 - Diamond Open Access
 - Promoting balanced multilingualism in open science and scholarly communication
 - OPERAS National Nodes as essential structural elements for Research Infrastructures
 - OPERAS-PLUS and its efforts for bridging research & society
 - Research Assessment supported by OPERAS
- **Community Policy Briefs - Dec 2023 to Aug 2025:**
 - Dumouchel, S., Mounier, P., Arasteh-Roodsary, S. L., & OPERAS. (2025). **Addressing disinformation challenges: a critical effort to support freedom, democracies and trust.** Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15047331>
 - OPERAS, C. (2023). **Supporting European capacities for Social Sciences and Humanities academic publishing and scholarly communication: The role of OPERAS research infrastructure** (Version v01). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11505526>.
 - OPERAS, Fiorini, S., Da Silva Ferreira, N. H., & Leão, D. (2025). **Promoting balanced multilingualism in open science and**

²⁶ Waiting for approval from the EC to publish them. Once approved, they will be available in this list:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/operaseu/records?q=Policy%20brief&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=bestmatch>.

scholarly communication.

Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16918121>.

- o OPERAS, Töpfer, M., Caliman Fontes, L., Stone, G., & Wnuk, M. (2025). **Ensuring Local Needs & Strengthening Distributed Infrastructures: OPERAS National Nodes.** Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16918868>.

5.1.5. Scientific Conferences, workshops & external events

During the entire OPERAS-PLUS project period, a wide range of events and conferences were (co-)organised to disseminate results, engage stakeholders, and foster dialogue around open scholarly communication. In the following section, the most significant and impactful of these events are presented and described.

➤ *Conferences (co-)organised by OPERAS*

OPERAS Conference²⁷

Figure 26 - OPERAS conference banner

As outlined in the initial communication strategy, WP8 committed to organising one international conference during the second half of the OPERAS-PLUS project to present project outcomes and foster dialogue with a broad spectrum of stakeholders. The OPERAS Conference 2024, held from 24–26 April in Zadar, Croatia, fulfilled this objective by bringing together researchers, publishers, librarians, decision-makers, and service providers in an open, collaborative environment. Under the theme "*Opening collaboration for community-driven scholarly communication*", the event responded to the European Council's May 2023 call for transparent, equitable, and immediate access to scholarly publications. Framed by the Council's recognition of scholarly knowledge as a public good, the conference supported OPERAS' commitment to shaping a more inclusive and sustainable scholarly communication ecosystem for the SSH.

²⁷ See: <https://operas-eu.org/news-and-events/calendar-2/operas-conference-2024/>.

Organised by the OPERAS-PLUS project, the conference served as a platform to showcase the first results of the project and to engage the broader community in improving and expanding them. The programme included 12 workshops, 27 posters, 10 parallel sessions, 40 presentations, one high-level panel discussion, and three keynote speeches. An open call for contributions ensured broad participation and visibility for emerging innovations in open scholarly communication. The event was also linked to the Assembly of the Commons, reinforcing the connection between project results and OPERAS' wider governance and community-building efforts.

Global Summit on Diamond Open Access

Figure 27 - Global Summit on Diamond Open Access banner

A conference and roundtable were part of the Global Summit on Diamond Open Access (23–27 October 2023), a unique series of events exploring nine key themes in diamond open access scholarly communication. The summit brought together a global community of researchers, editors, universities, funders, libraries, learned societies, publishers, and policymakers committed to strengthening the diamond open access ecosystem. Building on worldwide initiatives, this first-of-its-kind summit served as a platform for shaping a collective way forward.

OPERAS played a leading role as one of the co-organisers of the summit, alongside Redalyc, UAEMéx, AmeliCA, UNESCO, CLACSO, cOAlition S, Science Europe and others.

As a key co-organiser, OPERAS contributed significantly to shaping the programme, fostering international collaboration, and reinforcing the global Diamond Open Access landscape through its active involvement in the summit.

➤ Conference/Event participation

OPERAS service presentations

The OPERAS Services Task Force orchestrated a series of events dedicated to showcasing and advancing the OPERAS services. These events brought the spotlight to the OPERAS service catalogue that is driving forward open scholarly communication in the Social Sciences and Humanities across the European Research Area. In the following, the main presentations are listed:

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

OPERAS Services Catalogue presentations:

- OPERAS Conference 2024 (April, Zadar) - Full catalogue
- E-RIHS Public Event (24 Sept, Florence) - Full catalogue
- CONFOA 2024 (01 Oct, Porto) - Full catalogue

Full events or presentations in events with a focus on each particular service:

GoTriple

- ATRIUM Mutual Learning Exercise on GoTriple (29 Apr 2025, Madrid)
- ATRIUM Researcher Forum on GoTriple (17 Oct 2024, Poznan)
- OPERAS-FR: National Node event on GoTriple (5 July 2024, online)
- Presentation at the TrustOn 2024 Workshop (26 Jun 2024, Brussels) - GoTriple

VERA

- Presentation at the Final conference of project “Citizen-Enhanced Open Science in Southeastern Europe Higher Education Knowledge Hubs (CeOS_SE)”. (October 30, 2024, Zagreb)
- CeOS_SE Workshop at the University of Turin (4 October 2024, Turin)
- VERA Workshop at the University of Macerata (1 October 2024, Macerata)
- Presentation at the Trieste Next festival (28 September 2024, Trieste)
- Presentation VERA at the UN Science Summit (17 Sep 2024, online)
- Presentation at the Liber Conference 2024 (4 Jul 2024, Limassol)
- Presentation at the TrustOn 2024 Workshop (27 Jun 2024, Brussels)
- Presentation at “Comunidades de Ciência Aberta na UC” (6 May 2024, Coimbra)

PRISM

- OPERAS-UK: PRISM (5 June 2025, online)
- GraspOS Webinar on PRISM (14 May 2024, online)
- OPERAS-GER: Unlocking Monographs: The Way to Openness - An open access books day with DOAB-OAPEN (07 March 2023, Bonn)
- PRISM webinar (06 March 2023, online)

Metrics

- GraspOS Webinar on Metrics (26 Nov 2024, online)

Pathfinder

- Lunchtime with OPERAS: Pathfinder (27 June 2025, online)

Innovation Lab

- Future of OPERAS Innovation Lab, Open Seminar (26 June 2025, online)

1st SSH Open Cluster Assembly

Since the conclusion of the SSHOC project²⁸ in April 2022, the SSHOC Governing Board has worked intensively to establish a sustainable governance structure for the SSH Open Cluster and to ensure its continued service to the SSH research community. In February 2023, the newly expanded Governing Board—comprising representatives from all relevant Social & Cultural Innovation ESFRI projects—held its first official meeting and laid the groundwork for future collaboration. OPERAS, represented by Maciej Maryl from IBL PAN, the OPERAS core member from Poland, is part of the Governing Board. As a next step, the Board organised the 1st SSH Open Cluster Assembly, which was held virtually on 24 April 2023, to engage the broader community and discuss strategic directions for strengthening SSH collaboration in Europe.²⁹

Figure 28 - SSH Open Cluster banner

Science Summit

OPERAS participation in the Science Summit of the United Nations General Assembly began in September 2023 (UNGA78), in a session on people-centered science. On that occasion, OPERAS co-coordinator Suzanne Dumouchel made the bridge to diversity in publishing, Open Science and Diamond Open Access with her keynote “50th Anniversary of the Internet: People Centered Science and Digital Regulation leading to a People Centered Future”.

²⁸ See <https://sshopencloud.eu/project>.

²⁹ See:

<https://eosc.eu/events/1st-ssh-open-cluster-assembly/#:~:text=24%20April%202023&text=AI%20the%20participants%20in%20the,be%20held%20online%2C%20via%20Zoom>.

Figure 29 - Science Summit UNGA 78 banner

The participation continued in 2024, during the Science Summit of the 79th United Nations General Assembly (UNGA79), held in September 2024³⁰. OPERAS hosted an online session during the Summit, providing further insights and deepening the discussions of the TrustOn 2024 Workshop³¹ held in June in Brussels. The Summit session, “Fostering Trust in the Digital Sphere: A Multi-Stakeholder Approach Introduction”, explored innovative approaches and strategies to promote trustworthiness in digital interactions through multi-stakeholder collaboration.

OPERAS was also present within “The Digital Governance Series at the UN Science Summit 2024 - Transforming Science in the Age of AI and Digital Innovation” with a presentation on VERA in the session: “Defining Digital Citizen Science”, and participating in a discussion on Science Systems Humanity in the age of AI.

OPERAS participated, too, at different **international conferences**, addressing diverse stakeholder groups (e.g. Digital Humanities Annual Conference, PUBMET, Open Access Scholarly Publishers Association (OASPA), OpenScience, OpenScience FAIR, Munin Conference, Open Archives Initiative (OAI), EuroScience Open Forum (ESOF), and more), and on smaller workshops on national and international levels. This was done by the whole consortium.

➤ *OPERAS Workshops & Webinars*

Highlights of the Special Interest Groups (SIGs)

Advocacy Special Interest Group

Workshop “*Advocacy for Responsible Research Assessment for the Social Sciences and Humanities*”:

This in-person workshop was organised as part of the OPERAS Conference in Zadar, Croatia, on 26 April 2024. As a follow up, the SIG published a guide on how

³⁰ See <https://operas.hypotheses.org/7453>.

³¹ See <https://operas-eu.org/news-and-events/calendar-2/truston-2024/>.

to reuse the workshop on Zenodo (see: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11669020>) and published a blog post (see: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/7395>).

Open Chat Series of the OPERAS Advocacy Special Interest Group:

This online Open Chat Series³² featured experts in advocacy and communication, researchers, publishers and other members of the SSH community, highlighting the connection of the SIG with OPERAS services, such as GoTriple³³ and the Innovation Lab³⁴. The series received some general communication support to promote the events from the OCT. During the open chats :

- Current trends in open scholarly communication were discussed,
- Innovative solutions and tools for publishers, researchers and scholarly institutions were also explored,
- Best practices in open digital scholarly publications were shared.

Figures 30 to 32- Open Chat Series banners

Multilingualism Special Interest Group and Open Access Books Network Working Group

Mutual Learning Exercise - Multilingualism & OABN:

The Mutual Learning Exercise on Multilingualism aimed at discussing how to put multilingualism into practice. The session comprised two parts. The first one was through the use of the OPERAS service Mondaecus³⁵, a collaborative translation platform. The platform was presented and the participants were invited to do a collaborative translation of the Guidelines on Multilingualism³⁶, produced in the DIAMAS project. The second part focused on the ongoing blog series Around the world with the OABN³⁷.

³² See <https://operas-eu.org/special-interest-groups/advocacy-2/how-to-advocacy/>.

³³ See <https://www.gotriple.eu/>.

³⁴ See <https://lab.operas-eu.org/>.

³⁵ See <https://mondaecus.com/>.

³⁶ See <https://zenodo.org/records/13786094>.

³⁷ See

<https://openaccessbooksnetwork.hcommons.org/category/around-the-world-with-the-oabn/>.

Figure 33 - OPERAS MLE banner

Tools and Platforms Special Interest Group

AI and LLMs as tools for open scholarly communication in social sciences and humanities:

Organised as a webinar and made permanently available on Youtube³⁸, the aim was to present different initiatives from the OPERAS community related to AI. It included presentations of the LUMEN³⁹ & GRAPHIA⁴⁰ projects, the OPERAS Innovation Lab Accelerator, Open Book Publishers' experience with AI and some other examples of the use of LLMs in Social Sciences.

OA Book Special Interest Group

Lunchtime with

OPERAS

Meet the new

OA Books

Special Interest Group

March 3, 12h CET

Figure 34 - Lunchtime with OPERAS banner

In 2024, a new Special Interest Group, “Open Access Book”, was founded with three different Working Groups - OABN, Business Models and Open Infrastructures. The new SIG was publicly presented in a webinar on 3 March 2025.

5.1.6. Website

The OPERAS website⁴¹, as the main communication channel for the infrastructure, provides comprehensive information on the governance structure and legal

³⁸ See <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UNjvND3OGIq&t=1809s>.

³⁹ See <https://lumenproject.eu/>.

⁴⁰ See <https://graphia-ssh.eu/>.

⁴¹ OPERAS RI website: www.operas-eu.org.

entity, as well as details about its members and the various assemblies that make up the infrastructure. Additionally, the website consolidates information on Special Interest Groups, services, projects, news, events, and OPERAS' international partnerships.

The aim of the OPERAS website during the project was to serve as the central reference point for both the general public and all stakeholders seeking up-to-date information about the infrastructure and its activities.

Several new pages were added to the website and some updated completely:

- **OPERAS National Nodes** (*new*): lists all thirteen National Nodes, including information about each Nodes' lead institution(s), contact(s), social media, and their personalised logo.
- **Our commitment** (*new*): shows OPERAS' commitment to advancing open scholarly communication in the Social Sciences and Humanities by aligning with major European initiatives such as the Barcelona Declaration, CoARA, EOSC, and the Diamond OA Action Plan. Through these commitments, OPERAS strengthens its role as a trusted, sustainable Research Infrastructure promoting multilingualism, equity, and collaboration across Europe.
- **Services** (*updated*): on the landing pages, services have been grouped into relevant categories encompassing discovery, analytics, research for society, and quality assurance. Each of the six services has a new subline and an individual webpage refreshed, with a list of key features added at the top.
- **Projects** (*updated*): all current projects are presented with a list of key details (e.g. duration, number of partners, website) as well as a short description, partners' list and the main outcomes.
- **Living book** (*updated*): new papers were added, most recently in 2024, 'Diamond Open Access in Scholarly Publishing' and 'Open Access Policies – PALOMERA.'

In addition, following the key results from the 2024 communications workshop and interviews with National Nodes, the need for a comprehensive update of the OPERAS website became evident, also to improve SEO. When Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC), which has strong technical expertise in web development, joined OPERAS as a member in December 2024, discussions began around redesigning and modernising the website. Since April 2025, PSNC has contributed to this effort through a partly in-kind donation, focusing on improving the website's visual appearance, design, user experience and navigation. The communication team is working on the restructuring and update of the website content. The **new website** is scheduled to go live in the last quarter of 2025.

Figure 35 - Preview of new OPERAS website design

5.1.7. Blog (posts, series)

Started as the project’s first website, the OPERAS blog⁴² is currently the primary platform where the main news from the infrastructure and its members are disseminated.

The OPERAS blog runs on the Hypotheses⁴³ platform, complementing the main website. Hypotheses is included in the OPERAS services catalogue.

Several blog series were launched during the OPERAS-PLUS project period:

- **Welcome posts for new OPERAS members:** since January 2025, these have also been published in the respective national languages to reach a broader audience.
- The blog series **“Spotlight on National Nodes”:** it presents the activities of the OPERAS National Nodes within their national contexts, highlighting their work, specificities, and the challenges they face. All posts in the series are published in both English and the respective national language, demonstrating OPERAS’ commitment to multilingualism in practice.

The **Road to FAIR blog** (see <https://roadtofair.hypotheses.org/>) was discontinued in October 2023 as it was originally an output of the Co-OPERAS project and no longer aligned with OPERAS’ current communication needs. FAIR-related activities are now promoted through other initiatives, such as the RDA Working Group “Multilingual Controlled Vocabularies in the SSH,” supported by the RDA TIGER project.

In total, **81 blog posts** were published during the OPERAS-PLUS project, and the blog received **47,338 visits** between September 2022 and the 21st of July 2025.

⁴² See <https://operas.hypotheses.org/>.

⁴³ See <https://hypotheses.org/>.

5.1.8. Newsletter

The OPERAS newsletter⁴⁴ was published quarterly (February, May, August/September, and November), with a special year-end edition released in December 2024.

During the project period, the design and structure of the newsletter were updated to improve clarity and alignment with strategic priorities and the new OPERAS design. The new format includes the following sections, reflecting the key areas of OPERAS' activities and outreach:

- OPERAS Research Infrastructure News
- Events and Engagement
- Community and Projects News
- European Diamond Capacity Hub
- Multimedia Outcomes

Figure 36: Preview of design of the Newsletter 02/2025

In total, **12** editions of the OPERAS newsletter were published within the project period: one in 2022 (3 in total, but only 1 since the project started in September 2022), four in 2023, five in 2024, and two in 2025. Over this time, the subscriber base grew from **390 to 635** (as of 18th of July 2025), which marks a significant increase of 62.82%. All editions of the OPERAS newsletter are available in the archive: <https://operas-eu.org/operas-newsletter-archive/>.

5.1.9. Social Media

The social media activities during the OPERAS-PLUS project have kept steady and increasingly aligned with the new focus topics presented in the previous sections. Specific campaigns were realised following this new strategy, to be presented in the following section.

⁴⁴ See <https://operas-eu.org/operas-newsletter>.

As towards the end of the OPERAS-PLUS project, OPERAS is active on LinkedIn (the social media account which has the most followers of OPERAS at this moment), Bluesky, Facebook, YouTube and Instagram.

5.1.9.1. New Social Media Strategy

A new social media strategy has been introduced with the goal to enhance the visibility of OPERAS, its activities and services, engage target audiences more effectively, and streamline content delivery across platforms. Following the redefinition and alignment of OPERAS topics, based on the SWOT analysis, the communication team organised the social media channels to include two main types of content: regular posts (such as events and news from the Research Infrastructure) and campaigns (focused on the OPERAS topics).

As also seen in the previous visual identity section, templates help streamline the content creation of the campaigns and regular posting. On the following table, we present a summary of the regular posting and campaigns, focusing on their goals, target groups and basic content guidelines. The format of each campaign has been presented earlier at this report and can be consulted on the Visual Identity section (3.1).

Table 3 – Organisation of content for the OPERAS regular posting and campaigns

Regular posting			
	Goal	Target Group	Content
Events	Get people to sign up for OPERAS events, lead to our calendar and website	Depends on the topic of the event	Emoji with calendar, present date (when), what (name of the event), who (who presents, who is organising) and provide link.
News	Informing the public, raising awareness of updates, lead to the OPERAS blog.	OPERAS community and stakeholders, general public.	Use the #OPERASNews and newspaper emoji, provide basics (when, what, who, link). News should also mention and tag collaborators. Write as people don't know about OPERAS, offering a low entry point. Explain concepts.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Campaigns			
	Goal	Target Group	Content
OPERAS: Community, SIGs, National Nodes	Raise awareness and explain the mission of OPERAS as an infrastructure	Researchers, publishers and libraries; OPERAS community and stakeholders; citizens	Curiosity content. Use hashtags depending on subcampaign (#OPERAS, #OPERASNationalNodes, #OPERAScommunity, #OPERASSIGs). Use schemes or overviews, community facts, hot topics for SIGs. Avoid acronyms. Integrate success stories and positioning of OPERAS.
Open Access Books (sub-campaign)	Raise awareness of the importance of books for the SSH. Advocating to integrate books into Open Science policies.	Researchers and policy makers	Same as Community campaign guidelines. Add #OABooks. Create a brief slogan.
Multilingualism (sub-campaign)	Raise awareness of the importance of multilingualism, especially in SSH. Show developments within the topic.	Researchers and policy makers	Same as OPERAS community campaign; add #Multilingualism. Create a brief slogan. "Bibliodiversity through multilingualism".

Campaigns			
	Goal	Target Group	Content
Research Assessment	Raise awareness of the importance of research assessment,	Researchers and policy makers.	Same as main campaign, add #ReformingRA.

(subcampaign)	advocacy, and support initiatives.		
Services	Engage and convert to each service. Inform and raise awareness of OPERAS services.	Researchers, publishers and libraries, OPERAS community and stakeholders, service providers.	Use #OPERASService. Create questions or storytelling of use cases to explain which problems can be solved with a given service. Use tagging with collaborators. Explain the basics of the service when presenting it and provide links.
Citizen Science (subcampaign)	Highlight Citizen Science as a pillar of Open Science, focusing on SSH.	Researchers and policy makers; citizens; journalists.	Same as main campaign, use #CitizenScience and #ParticipatoryResearch.
Innovation Lab (subcampaign)	Create awareness of the Innovation Lab and engage researchers to collaborate, develop pilots and accelerate projects.	Researchers, service providers, editors.	Same as main campaign, use #OPERASInnovationLab. Call for action with links and deadlines for participating in calls.

Campaigns

	Goal	Target Group	Content
Projects, including project events	Raise awareness and create engagement for projects in which OPERAS participates, highlighting OPERAS activities in them.	Researchers, project partners, general public, and other specific audiences depending on project topics.	Tag the project social media channel, present basic information (when, what, who, link), repeat the goals of the project and definition.
Diamond Open	Create a strong relation between OPERAS and	Publishers, researchers,	Present what Diamond OA is, how to support it. Bring

Access (EDCH)	Diamond Open Access.	funders, policymakers.	importance of the topic to the audience and update on what is being done. Tag projects: EDCH, ALMASI, CRAFT-OA, DIAMAS. Use #DiamondOA #EDCH
----------------------	----------------------	------------------------	--

5.1.9.2. Social Media Channels

The social media channels are OPERAS daily contact points for communication updates, engagement and sharing of news and campaigns, not only with the internal community, but functioning as a showcase for the whole public and the diversity of stakeholders in the digital space. The social media channels in use are chosen having in mind the presence of these publics, the type of discussions the platforms entail, the specificities of their communication flow, but also their basic affinity with OPERAS values. Considering all this, the main channels used by OPERAS on its path towards the end of the OPERAS-PLUS project are **LinkedIn and Bluesky**. OPERAS **YouTube** channel, while another important platform for video sharing, is still in its beginning, but has been receiving some growing attention and dedication from the OPERAS Communication Team, that has restructured its home, created a series of thumbnails, reorganised its playlist and is now consistently uploading new material from projects in which OPERAS participates. The team also keeps activity on **Facebook and Instagram**. Although these channels are not the most important ones, they guarantee an extended presence, targeting specific niches such as librarians and researchers in Europe (Facebook), and the junior researchers public (Instagram).

The OPERAS channel on **X (formerly Twitter)** was discontinued in January 2025 following a decision making process started at the end of 2024 in conjunction with the OPERAS Coordination Team and the Executive Assembly. The choice of discontinuing activity in the platform followed a series of issues after the change of its direction, giving space to hate speech and disinformation. Despite the considerable number of followers (3406 as of Dec 2024), the decision was taken by the majority of OPERAS Executive Assembly members.⁴⁵ The **Bluesky** channel ([@operaseu.bsky.social](https://operaseu.bsky.social)) was then created as an alternative for X, also due to a massive move of researchers from one platform to the other.

Regarding coordination of the content creation and sharing on social media, the OPERAS team uses a centralised Hootsuite⁴⁶ account, allowing users to view planned posts and to produce content more efficiently, since the platform contemplates different social media channels for scheduling and posting. As of the end of OPERAS-PLUS, it is possible to schedule and post on OPERAS channels

⁴⁵ See also OPERAS' statement on leaving X: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/8559> .

⁴⁶ See <https://www.hootsuite.com/> .

on LinkedIn, Facebook and Instagram via Hootsuite. However, the team has been considering moving to an alternative social media managing tool as Bluesky is not integrated yet.

Regarding engagement, the OPERAS Communication Team has been making an effort to work closely with the national communities. With the help of the monthly meetings of the National Nodes Committee (integrating representatives of the nodes and the Communication Team), announcements are shared and members are requested to apply them in their own language and style. There is also a growing effort to produce translated versions of important campaigns, such as for the 2024 Annual Report, when a series of posts was prepared and translated to the 13 languages of the National Nodes.

Below, we further detail each channels' contribution to the communication strategy of OPERAS.

LinkedIn

Figure 37 - OPERAS top banner on LinkedIn page

The OPERAS page on LinkedIn⁴⁷ has been gaining more traction since the beginning of OPERAS-PLUS, and even more during the last year of the project, also following on the massive withdrawal of many scientists and scholars from X in 2024. As LinkedIn is a professional network, most of OPERAS' stakeholder groups are connected on this platform.

The new strategy for LinkedIn is summarised as follows.

Objective / purpose

- Increase brand awareness (European Research Infrastructure in the Social Science and Humanities; trusted advisor for Open Science and Open Access)
- Generate link leads
- Networking, interaction

Target groups

- Important Organisations in the European Research Area
- Research Performing Organisations, SSH researchers

⁴⁷ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/operas/>

- Policy makers, funders
- Publishers
- Librarians
- Service users
- Journalists

Content

- News/announcements
- Events (to register and provide reflection after they happen)
- Statements
- Elaborations on OPERAS related topics
- Reposting of OPERAS members (related to OPERAS activities) and posts about collaboration.

Format

- Statements
- Elaborations on topics
- Short texts
- Images and links, whenever possible

Frequency of posting

- 3-4 times a week

Bluesky (new channel, started in 2025)

Figure 38 - OPERAS top banner on Bluesky page

As explained at the beginning of the section, the Bluesky profile of OPERAS is the newest one. Therefore, the channel is still in its early phase. Nonetheless, OPERAS has as of July 2025 915 followers on Bluesky, which is a considerable

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

amount for a short period of time (in comparison, X/Twitter had 3,000 followers over a course of 7 years of activity).

The summary of the OPERAS strategy for Bluesky is as follows.

Objective / purpose:

- Interaction and reposting from members and partners, and community & answering
- Posting about everyday updates and events
- Create more engagement with OPERAS stakeholders and community
- Create and strengthen the community aspect of OPERAS.

Target group:

- OPERAS community
- Researchers and students (RPOs)
- OPERAS members/individuals
- Librarians
- Publishers
- Citizens
- Service users

Content:

- Useful content (e.g. SIGs activities, services updates, publications etc.)
- Add a more personal touch/tone
- Events sharing (registration)
- Events sharing (during)
- Reposting of reflections from members and participants
- Project resharing / project sharing (interactive)
- Outputs / publications
- News on services

Format

- Short texts
- Images or links, whenever possible

Frequency of posting

- Daily basis (for interaction)
- 3 times a week for posting
- Live posting at events

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

YouTube (revamped in 2024-2025)

Figure 39 - OPERAS home page top on YouTube channel

As stated before, the YouTube channel of OPERAS RI was reanimated in the final stage of OPERAS-PLUS, passing through a recalibration of playlists, the creation of thumbnails and the reactivation of uploads. A brief summarisation of a YouTube strategy is below.

Objective / purpose:

- To inform about OPERAS, OPERAS projects or fiscal hosting and OPERAS services and the community
- To display the projects videos and event videos
- To upload and promote OPERAS RI videos and tutorials

Target group:

- Community
- SSH researchers
- Service users
- OPERAS internal community

Content:

- Presenting OPERAS in videos with members (after completion of OPERAS-PLUS)
- Showing functions of the services
- Presenting projects via projects videos
- Displaying recordings of webinars and events
- Retrospective in the end of the year

Frequency of posting:

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Variable, depending on availability of new project videos. One retrospective per year with small videos, started in 2024.

Facebook and Instagram

Although the team created specialised strategies for both of these channels, we later decided to focus on our main platforms: LinkedIn, Bluesky, and YouTube. Therefore, by the end of OPERAS-PLUS, the strategies for Facebook and Instagram have been phased out, as these platforms were not generating significant reach or engagement. There is also an ongoing discussion about closing these channels, since the strategies we have in mind still require human resources that are currently lacking.

Summary of Instagram strategy:

Figure 40 - OPERAS instagram top home page

Objective / purpose:

- Attract SSH researchers and build relationships with them via OPERAS topics
- Provide useful information for them on Open Science topics (statistics for example), but with a focus on SSH

Target group:

- SSH researchers
- All the other stakeholders in their leisure time

Content:

- OPERAS related topics
- Important highlights that are shareable

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

- Curiosity content targeted at young researchers and addressing the needs of this target group, e.g. explanatory content about OA and OS
- Content should be low entry to OPERAS topics
- Ask questions in the content

Format:

- Quotes with people's pictures on certain topics
- Design: creating a new identity, using colors to give highlights on text, or coloring pictures (3 types of templates for different purposes)

Frequency of posting

- 2-3 times a week

Summarisation of Facebook strategy:

Figure 41 - OPERAS Facebook top home page

Objective / purpose:

- To inform about OPERAS topics for relevant stakeholders
- To share practical information work-related for stakeholders

Target group:

- Librarians
- Publishers
- SSH researchers / professors

Content:

- Presenting relevant topics for national communities
- Sharing Open Science good practices
- Informative banners + text
- Events (before they happen, to share registration is open)

Frequency of posting

- 1-2 posts a week

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

5.1.10. Other Communication Materials

In addition to communication content prepared for the various channels, several other materials were developed to support the visibility and outreach of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure and strengthen it. These include an institutional video⁴⁸ introducing OPERAS and its mission, a dedicated service video⁴⁹ highlighting the infrastructure's offerings, and a retrospective video series including 14 videos⁵⁰ capturing key moments and developments from 2024. Furthermore, a flyer was created to provide a concise and accessible overview of OPERAS, suitable for events and stakeholder engagement. These materials contribute to a more comprehensive and engaging communication toolkit, supporting both internal use and external promotion.

OPERAS Retrospective 2024 ▶ Alle wiedergeben

Join us for the OPERAS Retrospective 2024! Throughout December, we're sharing a series of videos celebrating key moments, milestones, advancements, and challenges in open scholarly...

Figure 42 - Retrospective series with 14 videos

Figure 43 - OPERAS Flyer

⁴⁸ See <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SWe7WvJdYSg>.

⁴⁹ See https://youtu.be/_TGYRDT-C7E.

⁵⁰ See https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLNSNTI1cPt5bj2iP_z3ZP5IXBuxfkkpiu.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Figure 44-45 - OPERAS image video and OPERAS services video

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

5.2. Indicators for communication

The initial table from deliverable 8.1 has been updated and inserted below to show which communication targets have been reached. The table below briefly introduces the key performance indicators (KPIs) used to measure the success of the communication and dissemination measures.

Table 4 - KPIs to measure the success of the communication and dissemination measures - updated and expanded with current numbers in July 2025

Channel / Engagem ent	Activity	Inform/ engage	Target Groups	Key Performa nce Indicator s (KPI)	Measure	1st year of the project (09/2022 - 08/2023)	2nd year of the project (09/2023 - 08/2024)	3rd year of the project (09/2024- as of 21.07.2025)	Average per month/ year	In total (09/2022 - 07/2025)	Status
OPERAS website	Main access point for RI and project results, links to other engagements with an event calendar for the community	inform	All stakeholders defined before	# unique visitors	> 800/ month	25.780 (per year)	34.570 (per year)	33.917 (per year)	2.716 (month)	94.267	reached

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Channel / Engagement	Activity	Inform/engage	Target Groups	Key Performance Indicators (KPI)	Measure	1st year of the project (09/2022 - 08/2023)	2nd year of the project (09/2023 - 08/2024)	3rd year of the project (09/2024- as of 21.07.2025)	Average per month/year	In total (09/2022 - 07/2025)	Status
OPERAS blog	news, community posts, different series, i.e. from the Special Interest Groups	engage	all stakeholders	# of posts	> 15/year	25	30	26	27 (year)	81	reached
				# unique visitors	> 2.500/month	18.681	18.246	10.411	1.364 (year)	47.338	reached
Newsletter	news	inform	all stakeholders, but especially for OPERAS members	# of newsletters	> 3 times/year	3	4	5	4 (year)	12	reached
				# of subscribers	> 50 new/year > 500 subscribers	458	519	635	-	635	reached
Social media	Regular posting of relevant news	inform	community, all stakeholders	# tweets (incl. retweets)	>300/year	269	301	127* (X page discontinued in January 2025)	24 (month)	697	reached with limitations (page inactivated)

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Channel / Engagement	Activity	Inform/engage	Target Groups	Key Performance Indicators (KPI)	Measure	1st year of the project (09/2022 - 08/2023)	2nd year of the project (09/2023 - 08/2024)	3rd year of the project (09/2024- as of 21.07.2025)	Average per month/year	In total (09/2022 - 07/2025)	Status
				# twitter followers	> 30 new followers/month	3,160	3,442	3,240	-	3,240	
The road to FAIR blog	regular posts on FAIR topics	engage	community	# of posts # of authors	> 20/year > 5	<i>The road FAIR blog was stopped (see section 5.1.7)</i>					
Events	international conference face-to-face	engage	community, Special Interest Groups	# participants	> 120	-	149	-	-	-	reached
	Virtual workshops		community, researchers, service provider, librarians, publishers	#workshops internal and external	< 50	35 (in 2022) No data available	47 (in 2023) 1.294 (in 2023)	45 (in 2025) 839 (in 2025)	-	127 (2022-2024)	reached

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Channel / Engagement	Activity	Inform/engage	Target Groups	Key Performance Indicators (KPI)	Measure	1st year of the project (09/2022 - 08/2023)	2nd year of the project (09/2023 - 08/2024)	3rd year of the project (09/2024- as of 21.07.2025)	Average per month/year	In total (09/2022 - 07/2025)	Status
			, policymakers	# participants							
Campaigns	Planned communication campaign on several channels	inform	Researchers, Research Performing Organisations, Librarians, Publishers	#campaigns	3	-	2	2	-	4	reached
Policy briefs	short papers to different topics	inform	national ministries, Social Sciences and Humanities research policymakers	# briefs	< 5	-	1	5	-	5	reached

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Within Work Package 8 of the OPERAS-PLUS project, task 8.2 involved creating a dashboard to monitor the impact and performance of OPERAS activities, including communication activities. The communication indicators have also been presented there in an interactive and user-friendly format within the dashboard, enabling more detailed visualisation & better monitoring of communication activities. A preview of the interactive dashboard is presented below. More details can be found in Deliverable 8.7. of work package 8.

Figures 46 & 47 - Preview of the monitoring performance dashboard, presenting the communication indicators

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

6. Post-OPERAS-PLUS: Reflections & Strategy

6.1. Coordination of all communication activities - toward a sustainable communication framework for OPERAS

As highlighted in the previous communication strategy in D8.1, OPERAS faces a number of inherent risks in its communication landscape — including fragmentation due to rapid growth, potential stakeholder disengagement, and the challenge of maintaining consistency across diverse actors and activities. These risks underscore the need to move beyond a project-based approach and treat communication as a strategic, transversal function within the Research Infrastructure.

To minimise these challenges and ensure readiness for the transition to ERIC status, it is recommended that communication takes a stronger role within OPERAS structure. Strategic communication plays a vital role not only in increasing visibility but also in fostering internal cohesion, enabling knowledge uptake, and maintaining trust with stakeholders. This is particularly critical as the infrastructure continues to scale and coordinate more complex, multi-stakeholder activities.

Such a function requires dedicated leadership, structural support, and long-term coordination across OPERAS' services, National Nodes, and projects, as well as the adequate provision of communication tools.

As OPERAS moves toward ERIC status, several future actions are proposed to reinforce the communication coordination:

1. Strengthen the coordination of OPERAS communication activities:

- Set up a new and long-term structure of the communication coordination that ensures effectiveness.
- Involve different sections into the communication activities to align messaging across efforts, e.g. the Advocacy Special Interest Group, the communication officers of all projects OPERAS is involved in, as well as with communication staff from other Research Infrastructure in the SSH.

2. Strengthen identity consistency and visibility:

- Integration of “success stories” and “use cases” into the new OPERAS website, communication material and campaigns.
- Ensure all communication materials follow a coherent tone, messaging framework, and visual style to build recognition across stakeholder groups and countries, also within national communities.
- Implement some automated communication processes such as e.g. an OPERAS AI prompt guide for communication.

3. Deepen stakeholder engagement & commitment of countries for the ERIC:

- Leverage the developed personas to tailor content, tone, and channel choices for specific audiences, particularly during the pre-ERIC advocacy phase.

- Organise regular thematic campaigns (e.g. national success stories, impact features, service highlights, community voices) to sustain interest.
- Continue producing Community Policy Briefs that align with national agendas and policy opportunities.
- Translate key policy briefs as well as other communication material into local languages of the National Nodes to increase accessibility, credibility, and policy relevance at the member state level, as well as to strengthen multilingualism.
- Introduce an “ERIC Countdown” or “ERIC Pathway” section on the new website to explain the ERIC process, highlight milestones, and engage stakeholders.

6.2. National Nodes & local communication strategy

In future projects, the coordination and strategic alignment of communication efforts with the National Nodes should be more deeply integrated from the beginning. National Nodes play a vital role in bridging central project objectives with local and national research communities. Strengthening this relationship can significantly amplify the visibility, relevance, and impact of communication activities across Europe.

To support this, the following action areas are recommended:

1. Capacity building and strategic alignment

- To ensure a shared understanding of messaging and tools, training or briefing sessions should be offered to National Nodes. These could cover updates on the overall communication strategy, audience personas, and the use of common tools such as policy brief templates and key messaging guides. This should be additional to the meeting within the National Node committee.
- A dedicated “National Node Comms Kit”—including ready-to-use materials such as standard slide decks, press release templates, infographics, and FAQs within each national node language could help to ensure consistency and efficiency in local outreach while enabling flexibility for national contexts.

2. National engagement campaigns

- Future communication strategies should actively support National Nodes in tailoring and disseminating Community Policy Briefs and OPERAS services aligned with national priorities or political developments.
- Where possible, projects should co-develop country-specific campaigns or success stories that highlight OPERAS-related impact.

6.3. Recommendations for future projects

Based on the experiences and lessons learned throughout the OPERAS-PLUS project, the following recommendations are proposed to strengthen

communication in future initiatives, particularly those working toward long-term impact and community engagement.

1. Invest in audience research and personas

A clear understanding of the target audiences is essential for meaningful engagement. Future projects should prioritise the development or refinement of audience personas early on, using them to guide stakeholder mapping, content planning, and message tailoring. Sufficient time and resources should be allocated for interviews, feedback loops, and iterative testing to ensure that communication remains relevant and effective throughout the project lifecycle and beyond.

2. Foster national-level engagement beyond translation

National outreach should go beyond simple translation. Engaging National Nodes as co-creators of content and strategy within projects — rather than just amplifiers — enables deeper connection with local communities and enhances relevance. Tailored national strategies, built on collaboration, are key to ensuring that messages resonate in diverse policy and research landscapes.

3. Develop sustainable, modular communication

Future projects should aim to produce adaptable and reusable communication materials, potentially including automated elements — e.g., specific AI prompts for OPERAS communication, an AI agent for gathering press releases on OPERAS, Hootsuite integration, streamlining dissemination, gathering feedback from events, etc. For example, this could involve evaluating and implementing actions to automate and innovate OPERAS' communication management and processes.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains